

The Effect of the European Green Deal on American Companies Exporting to the European Union

Eline DEWANCKELE^a

a: Researcher, İstanbul Ticaret University, 0009-0003-3032-3134, eline.dewanckele89@gmail.com

Submitted: 07.12.2025, Accepted: 30.03.2026, Published: 25.04.2026

Cite APA: Dewanckele, E., (2026). The Effect of the European Green Deal on American Companies Exporting to the European Union, Journal of İstanbul School of Technology (JISTECH), 2(1), pp 56-72, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19654789

ABSTRACT

This thesis examines the impact of the European Green Deal (EGD) on American companies exporting to the EU. The aim is to determine to what extent current European climate policies create trade barriers for U.S. exporters. The study combines literature research with quantitative data analysis, based on figures from Eurostat and United States International Trade Commission (USITC) DataWeb. Theoretically, it shows that the EGD could lead to higher costs and adjustment pressure for U.S. companies. This is especially applicable for high-emitting sectors. However, no clear impact is visible in the trade data yet, which can be explained by the early phase of implementation. The results indicate that structural consequences are likely to become visible in the medium to long term. This underlines the need for strategic preparation by U.S. companies. Also at the same time, it highlights the importance for the EU to implement its policies carefully and to avoid creating unintended protectionist effects.

Keywords: *European Green Deal, U.S. exports, Trade barriers, Sustainability*

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change is being felt worldwide and is putting pressure on governments to take action. The European Union is leading the way with the European Green Deal, a strategy to become climate neutral by 2050 (European Commission, 2019). With measures such as the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), which attaches a carbon price to certain imported products, the impact of this policy extends beyond Europe's borders (Marcu, Mehling & Cosbey, 2020). It means for US companies exporting to the EU uncertainties. Especially since US climate policy is often seen as fragmented and unstable (Bacchus, 2022).. This causes complex situations to adapt to European environmental rules. While much research has been done on the overall impact of climate policy on trade, little attention has been paid to the concrete consequences for US exporters.

This study examines whether and how the European Green Deal affects the current export relationship between the United States and the EU. The next following chapter of this article will review the existing literature on the climate policy, EU-U.S. trade relation and research gap. Chapter 3 presents data on U.S. exports in relation to the EGD. Chapters 4 and 5 discuss and conclude the information found.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. European Green Deal

The EGD aims to make Europe climate neutral by 2050. This will result in notable changes that will impact international trade relations in addition to the European economy. The European Commission (2019) shows that the green deal combines a number of policy actions to lower emissions, protect biodiversity, and reduce pollution. The European Union uses its trade policy to achieve environmental aims. According to Sadeleer and Gauthier Martens (2022), the EU hopes to gain a "green" competitive advantage through this. It forces trading partners to increase the sustainability of their production by implementing stricter rules regarding the environment. This would boost European companies' market positions. At the same time, Felbermayr et al. (2024) express concern that this approach could interfere with trade flows. They note that non-EU countries that have difficulty adapting to the new regulations may be exposed to

increased expenses and trade restrictions. Besliu (2023) goes on to state that non-tariff trade barriers are a serious issue, particularly for developing countries.

The Emissions Trading System (ETS), established in 2005, is one of the EU's main instruments for reducing CO₂ emissions in the internal market. With the launch of the European Green Deal in 2019, this system was further strengthened. The Fit for 55 package was introduced. This package extends the scope of the ETS and introduces new measures to increase its effectiveness (European Commission, 2025b). One of these measures is the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), which is designed to create and guarantee fairness between EU producers and foreign companies exporting to the EU. CBAM adds a carbon price to imported goods based on their emissions in the supply chain (European Commission, 2025a). According to Dechezleprêtre et al. (2025), this mechanism helps prevent carbon leakage by discouraging companies from relocating their production to countries with more flexible environmental regulations. There is criticism of CBAM despite its potential. Engström (2022) questions if CBAM will result in global carbon reductions because certain trading partners may view the move as protectionist. Bardt and Kolev (2021) also highlight the logistical and financial difficulties of implementing such regulations globally. As a result, the EGD's success is dependent on the willingness to engage with trading partners outside of the EU (Dmirbilek et al., 2018).

At the same time, there are also positive views from academics on the global impact of the EGD. Delbeke et al. (2020) argue that the EU's ambitious climate targets could stimulate other countries to implement stricter environmental regulations. This view is supported by the World Economic Forum (2020), which reports that many companies are already adapting their production in anticipation of European requirements. The EGD can be viewed as an example in this sense. Both EU and non-EU nations develop unity in this regard and adjust to European environmental laws.

2.2. EU-U.S. trade

The EU-US trade relationship has changed over time. It is no longer just about trade, but also about climate policy and sustainability. This change is driven by changing political priorities, domestic interests and international developments. These factors play a major role on both sides of the Atlantic. Since the 1990s, the U.S. has led attempts to improve regional commerce through agreements such as NAFTA. These agreements were used to stimulate economic growth. However, they failed to properly address environmental challenges. For instance, in order to address environmental concerns, the North American Agreement on Environmental Cooperation (NAAEC) was established alongside with NAFTA. Nevertheless, the NAAEC was unable to effectively control pollution or protect natural resources due to its lack of enforcement capabilities, particularly in the industrial border regions Charnovitz (1994). Bacchus (2022) notes that this demonstrates how the United States frequently prioritized economic growth over environmental protection in its trade policy.

In the contrary, the EU has established itself as a leader in sustainable trade policy from the beginning. The European Union uses the European Green Deal as a mean of achieving net zero emissions by 2050 (European Commission, 2019). In order to guarantee that trade not only encourages economic growth but also advances climate goals, the EU included environmental standards into its trade agreements (Ville, 2025). The EU operates under the belief that trade must be responsible for the environment and the economy (Louisa-Maria, 2024). Trade barriers may result from this in the short term, but they are considered to be an essential step in the long run to guarantee sustainability and fair competition.

The U.S. has shown a varying and frequently hesitant approach to climate policy in contrast to the EU. Due to economic concerns, the nation withdrew from the Kyoto Protocol under President Bush (2001–2009) (Cohen & Egelston, 2003). However, the Obama administration (2009–2017) attempted to balance economic growth and climate protection through programs like the Clean Power Plan (Workman et al., 2020). As

further noted by Wentz & Gerrard (2019) and Swain et al. (2025), this policy uncertainty led to disagreements in transatlantic collaboration and impacted the EU's trust in the United States as a reliable climate partner.

During the Transatlantic Trade and Investment Partnership (TTIP) negotiations, tensions between the United States and the European Union were visible. To save the environment, the EU insisted on strict rules related to the environment (Peterson, 2016). But according to Beckman et al. (2021), the United States saw these rules as barriers to free trade. Peterson (2016) and Lucatello (2022) claim that the failure of TTIP demonstrates the clear differences in the two areas' approaches to policy. As reflected later in the USMCA agreement, the United States favored looser environmental laws (Bacchus, 2022). The collapse of the TTIP negotiations was mainly caused by the conflict over environmental regulation.

The Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), which the EU recently introduced, has heightened tensions between the U.S. and the EU. The EU sees CBAM as an essential tool in order to meet its climate goals and stop carbon leakage (European Commission, 2025a). Nevertheless, U.S. officials fear that CBAM would unfairly hinder U.S. exports and lead to trade problems, functioning as a type of protectionism (Stephansson, 2023). According to Keskin (2025), CBAM places a great deal of pressure on American businesses that produce large amounts of carbon emissions, which hinders their ability to compete globally.

Climate policy in the United States is uneven because of regional and political differences. Some states are leading the way in reducing emissions and developing renewable energy as California. On the other hand, states that are rich in oil, like Wyoming and Texas, frequently protest federal climate changes (Bergquist & Warshaw, 2023). Despite the Biden administration's prior strengthening of international collaboration and climate initiatives, the Trump administration's reelection indicates a change in plans. The U.S. finds it challenging to continuously align with the EU on

climate-related trade and environmental goals due to this ongoing absence of national consensus (Sinkkonen & Martin, 2021; Gibson, 2025).

2.3. Research gap

With a focus on the United States, Figure 1 highlights the primary research gaps in the currently available academic literature about the green deal and its effects on American exporters. The majority of current research focuses on others countries in continents like Asia, Africa, and Latin America. These studies regularly bring attention to issues with national strategy, inequality, and adaptation to the rules of the EU. Despite being one of the EU's most important trading partners, the United States receives less attention. When the U.S. is mentioned, the focus tends to remain at the policy level. There is a lack of sector-specific data or measurable trade outcomes that show how American companies are impacted in practice. A few studies use concrete trade data to explore changes.

In order to close that gap, this thesis combines a quantitative study of trade data with a review of the literature. It examines the sectors most impacted by EGD and focuses on U.S. exports to the EU. This study offers a data-driven viewpoint that sheds light on how the United States is reacting to the changing environmental situation in the European Union and what this means for future trade between the two economies.

Table 1. Literature Gap

Research Area/Topic	Existing Literature Insights	Identified Research Gaps	Research Focus for this thesis	Sources
Policy and theory on the EGD	Mostly theoretical and policy-oriented	Lacks concrete data on trade impacts	Adds a practical view with trade data, focused on the U.S.	Lucatello (2022); European Commission (2019); Amendola (2025)
Regional focus: non-	Focus on countries from other	U.S. impact often overlooked	Focuses on U.S. exports and how they are affected	Wenmei en Wang (2023);

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EU countries	continents as Asia, Africa, Latin America			Clair (2022); Zoghbi (2022); Peña-Ramos et al. (2021); Karkare & Medinilla (2023)
Impact on U.S. companies	Emphasis on politics and policy alignment	Few insights on affected sectors or adaptation	Combines literature and data to assess sector preparedness	Stephansson (2023); Rossetto (2023); Lashof & Neuberger (2023)
Quantitative impact assessment	Risks mentioned but little numerical trade data	Lack of measurable, sector-specific export insights	Uses 2019–2024 data to analyze trends and potential impact	Bergquist & Warsaw (2023); Stephansson (2023)

2. ANALYSIS

In order to better understand the literature research, a quantitative study was conducted on the impact of the EGD on American companies exporting to the EU. Figures were collected for the period from 2019 to 2025. This period was chosen to study export behavior before and after the EGD. Where necessary, the figures are examined per month to know exactly whether or not there was an impact at important dates in the early stages of the EGD. The figures on exports to the EU come from Eurostat. The export figures for the United States come from the official database of the United States International Trade Commission (USITC).

Figure 1. EU27 Import Value by Continent (European Commission, 2025c)

The first graph looks at exports to the EU from different continents with the United States as a separate line. The continent of Asia stands out head and shoulders above the other continents. In addition, this continent reacts most sensitively every time a major event takes place in the EGD process. This reaction indicates a certain sensitivity to the green deal. It is also remarkable that the U.S. maintains a stable export trend throughout the entire early stage of the EGD. This indicates that American exporters are less influenced by European policy developments.

Figure 2. EU27 Import Value from the U.S., China and the Rest of Asia (European Commission, 2025c)

The second graph takes a closer look at the Asian continent, which the previous graph showed to be more affected by major EGD events. The continent is divided into China and the rest of Asia and compared to the U.S.. China and the rest of Asia show a slight decline after the announcement of the EGD. This pattern is also visible in the first levy implementation of the CBAM. In contrast to the U.S., there is little to no decline in export volumes to the EU. These findings indicate that Asian countries are more sensitive to European legislation.

Figure 3. Distribution of U.S. exports in 2019 and 2024 (USITC, 2025)

In addition to the geographical insights, the distribution of U.S. exports was also examined. Data from the USITC form two pie charts. One from 2019 and one from 2024. These show that the position of certain European countries as buyers of U.S. products has even been strengthened. For example, the Netherlands rises significantly in rank and Germany maintains its strong position. Both countries are known as proponents of strict climate policy within the EU. This increase suggests that climate policy has not hampered transatlantic trade so far. On the contrary, it looks like U.S. exporters can still successfully continue to sell their products in the beginning stage of the EGD.

Figure 4. Evolution of U.S. exports to the EU27 by sector (2019-2024) (USITC, 2025)

The graph in figure 4 that places the most climate-sensitive sectors next to each other, also confirms the previous findings. These sectors are mining and minerals, chemicals, plastics and rubber, metal products, machines and vehicles. The export volume of each sector is compared in 2019 and 2024. An increase was observed in all sectors, some sectors more than others. This means that American companies, despite the preparations for the CBAM and other climate regulations, are not losing their position on the European market. Although the analysis of quantitative data reveals trends, there are also methodological limitations. First the data ends in 2024 or early 2025. As a result, the full effect of the CBAM is not visible. Furthermore, the analysis does not take into account seasonal influences, exchange rate fluctuations or geopolitical disruptions. Changes in export volumes cannot be attributed 100% to climate policy. Nevertheless, the current insights provide a basis for understanding the impact of the EGD on U.S. exporters to the EU.

These findings raise important questions for future research. Will U.S. companies be able to maintain their competitive position when the financial effects of the CBAM are felt?

And how will Asian countries further adapt their trade strategies to the increasing European sustainability demands? The answers to these questions will only become clear in the coming years (Öz, 2020).

3. DISCUSSION

The results of the quantitative analysis show that the implementation of the EGD has not yet caused clear shifts in trade between the United States and the European Union. On the contrary, U.S export volumes to the EU continue to grow. This suggests that the implementation phase of the green deal does not yet pose direct barriers for the American companies.

When examining the geographical distribution of exports to the EU, it is clear that Asian nations are responding more strongly to green deal policy developments. Export volumes from China and other Asian countries temporarily decline in the months surrounding the most important events of the EGD. This continent Asia is exporting the most to the EU. This can suggest that countries who are exporting a lot to the EU, are more vulnerable for the green deal. In comparison, U.S. exports were mostly stable during the same period. They even show a slight growth in certain months. US exporters appear to be less sensitive to short-term European policy developments.

Furthermore, the analysis shows that two EU countries are in the top 8 of U.S. export destinations. These two countries are the Netherlands and Germany. Both countries increase in export share between 2019 and 2024. The higher position of the Netherlands in 2024 is very remarkable. This shows that a European focus remains in the U.S., even though initial measures have already been implemented in the early stages of the EGD. Sector analyses also indicate a rising pattern. Between 2019 and 2024, exports from industries that are sensitive to climate change, like metals, machinery, cars, and chemical products, increased. There are several reasons for this growth. For instance, the recovery from the coronavirus epidemic had a significant impact on trade volume. Furthermore, supply chain reorganizations and changes in global market prices may have an impact on

the numbers. It is not possible to say with certainty from the data if this increase is the consequence of a proactive adjustment to European climate regulations.

An key methodological aspect to note is that the time period researched, from 2019 to March 2025, was carefully chosen to take into account both the situation before to the announcement of the green deal and the very first policy implementations. To properly detect structural trade trends, it is still a quite short time frame. Numerous EGD measurements are still in their infancy. As a result, bigger impacts might not be visible right away. Furthermore, outside variables that continue to influence the interpretation of export data, make it challenging to separate the effects of the EGD.

4. CONCLUSION

The European Green Deal has so far had a minimal effect on U.S. exports to the European Union, according to the statistical analysis and the literature reviewed. The literature previously shown that climate measures may cause disruptions in international trade. Particularly in developing countries and in industries with significant emissions. But according to the numerical data, U.S. exports in climate-sensitive industries have grown since 2019.

One significant finding is that, in contrast to export flows from Asia, U.S. exports hardly react to EGD announcements. Although several studies, including those by Besliu (2023) and Felbermayr et al. (2024), warn of rising trade barriers brought on by climate policies, the U.S. export statistics show another perspective. This difference can be explained by a range of variables. One reason is the strong trade relationship between the EU and the U.S.. Another one is the overall competitiveness of U.S. companies. And lastly the fact that the green deal is still in progress.

Additionally, the literature emphasizes the importance of mutual adaptation. On one side, non-European countries must become aware of changes in the European market. On the other side, the EU must make sure that its climate policy is not interpreted as protectionist.

U.S. export growth shows that American companies can still trade easily with the European market. For now, EU rules do not seem to create major problems for them. However, it is unclear whether the current pattern will continue. The pressure on exporters can rise when the CBAM goes into effect and other green deal regulations are strengthened. Future economic ties between the U.S. and the EU will be affected by both the EU's application of its regulations and the speed at which U.S. companies can adjust. A balanced strategy is required to minimize perceived protectionism and ensure open, fair trade.

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